

Deliverable 5.5

Final Report on the second ERL Smart City competition

Project acronym:	SCIROC
Project number:	780086
Project title	European Robotics League plus Smart Cities Robot Competitions
WP number and title:	WP5 – Smart Cities competitions
WP leader:	Daniele Nardi – Sapienza Università di Roma (UNIROMA1)

Organisation responsible for deliverable:	Beneficiary 9 - Sapienza Università di Roma (UNIROMA1)
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Deliverable version number:	5.5
Actual delivery date:	14 January 2022
Dissemination Type	Report
Dissemination level:	Public

Change log			
Version	Date	Author	Reason for change
			Draft

Release approval			
Version	Date	Name and organisation	Role
1.0		Daniele Nardi – UNIROMA1	WP leader
1.0	12/01/2022	Sarah Carter - UWE Bristol	Project Manager
1.0	13/01/2022	Matthew Studley – UWE Bristol	Project Coordinator

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under grant agreement n° 780086

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List of acronyms

ERL	European Robotics League
FBM	Functional Benchmark
TBM	Task Benchmark
WP	Work Package
EP	Episode
LIS	Italian Sign Language

1.0 Introduction

SciRoc project, funded by EU-H2020, is supporting the introduction of robots in **Smart Cities** and, in particular, the **European Robotics League** (ERL) smart cities, whose aim is to promote and show how robots will be part of the cities of the future, acting both as mobile sensors and city actuators. This adds a new challenge to ERL, which is pursued through the organisation of two major events. The previous SciRoc Challenge took place in 2019 in Milton Keynes (UK). The second **Smart Cities RObotics Challenge** (the 2nd **SciRoc challenge**) was held in the city of **Bologna (Italy)** from **Sept 6th to Sept 10th, 2021**. This document is a complete report of the event of the second SciRoc challenge.

1.1 Overview of the present document

The deliverable consists of 4 main parts: a short introduction of Deliverable 5.5, a general presentation of the competition, a description of each of the five *episodes*, and its impact. More specifically

- **Section 1** briefly introduces the SciRoc project and the second SciRoc challenge.
- **Section 2** describes the city of Bologna, the competition venue at Palazzo Re Enzo, the organising team, the competition infrastructure, the schedule, the sponsors, the logistics for the participants, branding and trophies and co-located events.
- **Section 3** provides a description of the five episodes, where for each episode we report a description of the technical challenges, the participating teams, the preparation phase, the execution of the competition, including the preliminaries and the finals, results and lessons learned.
- **Section 4** describes the impacts of the competition including data about the visitors, the subjects involved in the experiments and the media coverage.

2.0 Second Robotic Competition in a Smart City

In this section, we provide a detailed description of the organisation of the SciRoc event in Bologna. Bologna was selected among several applicants through an open call process which is described in Deliverable 5.4. The development of the COVID-19 pandemics came right after the award to Bologna and it had a substantial impact on the organisation of the competition. After careful consideration of pros and cons concerning the feasibility of keeping the original planned schedule or postponing the event, the decision of keeping the original schedule was taken. An analysis of the difficulties caused by the pandemics and the implemented countermeasures is developed throughout the document.

2.1 Bologna

Bologna, located in the Emilia-Romagna region of Italy, is one of the most attractive Italian cities for tourists and academics from all over the world. It is also among the best cities to live in Italy thanks to its effective administration, reliable and efficient public services, inclusive attitude and multicultural society.¹

Beyond being a wonderful place to visit, Bologna is universally known as the city hosting the oldest European University, Alma Mater, one of the best Universities in Italy, and beyond. One of the magics of Bologna is that Alma Mater Studiorum is everywhere: it is impossible to stroll around the city without feeling the academic atmosphere, which makes it such a dynamic, young and multicultural place.

Bologna has also established a reputation of being an inclusive city, open to civic engagement and creative contributions. According to this tradition, it interprets the “Smart City” concept as an opportunity to improve services that guarantee fundamental rights to the community, such as sociality, education, development and health. This inclusivity was one of the key motivations in Bologna applying to host the SciRoc event, and ultimately where the theme of the 2021 event ‘Smart Inclusion’ developed.

2.2 The competition venue

The competition took place at Palazzo Re Enzo (Figure 1.1), a historical building located in Piazza Maggiore, the central square and heart of Bologna.

¹ <http://www.comune.bologna.it/>

Figure 1.1 Palazzo Re Enzo

The floor plan of the venue is shown below (Figure 1.2). The competition was spread across two rooms within the venue, Salone Del Podesta (room 1) and Sala Degli Atti (room 2) (Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.2 Palazzo Re Enzo Floorplan

Figure 1.3(a) Salone Del Podesta

Figure 1.3(b) Sala Degli Atti

2.3 The organising team

Competition organisation:

Coordination and supervision: Valentina Presutti, Ugo Dallolio

General organisation: Matthew Studley, Sarah Carter, Ian Pulford

Social media and dissemination: Sarah Carter

Volunteers: Valentina Presutti, University of Bologna research students

Technical committees:

Episode 1: Vincenzo Suriani, Daniel Puig, Daniele Nardi.

Episode 2: Emanuele Antonioni, Daniele Nardi, Lun Wang, Olga Caprici.

Episode 3: Matteo Matteucci, Giulio Fontana, Francesco Riccio, Enrico Piazza.

Episode 4: Francisco J. Perez Grau, Fernando Herrero, Alberto Sanfeliu.

Episode 5: Deebul Nair, Sven Schneider, Duncan Russell, Jelizaveta Konstantinova.

2.4 The competition layout and infrastructure

A competition arena was set up across both rooms within the venue. The arena was divided into a number of sub-areas to accommodate each episode, teams, staff and volunteers.

The central area in both rooms (highlighted in Figure 1.4) was designed to host the episodes. Episode arenas were cordoned off and not accessible to members of the public, however each episode arena had ample space surrounding it for audience members to watch as teams participated. The central area was also fitted with a stage used for daily briefings, presentations and demos.

Teams were provided with a dedicated working area (highlighted in Figure 1.4) composed of tables and chairs (a variable number depending on the team size), ethernet connection and power. These areas were also available to referees and staff members, and a separate office was also used for staff members and volunteers to work from.

A secure storage area was also available for teams to safely store their robots, equipment and any other materials. This storage area was locked at all times, with only the event organiser and venue manager having access keys.

Each episode arena was set up according to the specifications provided in the rulebooks:

- Episode 1 - Coffee shop. This arena, located in room 1, was fitted to replicate a coffee shop. With the help of our volunteers acting as customers, the arena was set up with tables & chairs and food & beverage props for the robots to deliver to customers. The arena also had a dedicated stream for remote teams to watch and participate, and a monitor for the audience in Bologna to watch the remote teams compete.
- Episode 2 - Sign language Generation/Interpretation. This arena, located in room 1, also had a dedicated stream for remote teams to watch and participate, and a monitor for the audience in Bologna to watch the remote teams compete. This episode was supported by LIS experts from the Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies (Figure 1.5), who also sponsored the 2021 event.

Figure 1.5 LIS experts from the Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies with TIAGo robot.

- Episode 3 - Shopping Cart. Located in room 2, this arena made use of a full size shopping cart to be navigated around obstacles within the arena. This episode used a monitor for remote participation and shared a stream with Episodes 4 and 5.

- Episode 4 - Delivery of Emergency Medicines. Located in room 1, the arena was set up as a maze to which the robot had to navigate its way through. This episode used a monitor for remote participation and shared a stream with Episodes 3 and 5.
- Episode 5 - Shopping Pick & Pack. Located in room 2 this episode, supported by Ocado, was set up to replicate a shopping experience with shelves containing grocery items for the robot to pick up and pack into boxes. This episode used a monitor for remote participation and shared a stream with Episodes 3 and 4.

2.5 Logistics for the participants

The SciRoc website included a page dedicated to team members containing all necessary information relating to the 2021 event including, travel information, accommodation options, links to information on COVID-19 regulations in Italy, robot loan scheme, shipping information for robots and equipment and episode-specific details.

Teams were contacted regularly by the SciRoc Project Manager leading up to the event with useful information and website links.

2.5.1 Accommodation options

All team members attending the 2021 event were offered discounts on accommodation for the duration of their stay in Bologna. Our hosts in Bologna worked with local hotel providers to offer a discounted rate for anyone attending the event.

2.5.2 Robot handling:

As a sponsor of the 2021 event, PAL Robotics offered teams the opportunity to loan a robot at a reduced cost using their loan scheme. PAL Robotics set up a dedicated web page containing details of the scheme and information on how to apply. PAL Robotics then organised the shipment of robots for teams who used the scheme.

Teams who did not use the loan scheme were responsible for shipping their own robots and equipment to the venue. The dedicated teams page on the SciRoc website contained shipping details and teams were encouraged to contact the SciRoc Project Manager with any shipping related questions.

All shipments were permitted to arrive at the venue on or after Thursday 2nd September where they were securely stored until the start of the competition. The venue manager at Palazzo

Re Enzo worked with SciRoc staff and teams to confirm receipt of all shipments. Return shipments were then arranged for Saturday 11th September following the completion of the competition.

2.6 Measures for COVID-19 pandemic

In order to ensure the safety of all participants at the SciRoc 2021 event, the following measures were taken:

- Everyone attending the event, including staff members and teams, were required to show a COVID-19 Digital Certificate as per Italian Regulations to enter the venue. This certificate indicates that the recipient has had at least one dose of vaccine *or* has received a negative (molecular or antigen) swab test within the previous 48 hours *or* has recovered from COVID-19 in the previous six months.
- All attendees at the event were required to wear a face covering at all times.
- Social distancing measures were in place throughout the event.
- Additional cleaning measures were in place at the venue, with regular cleaning taking place throughout the event and each evening.
- Co-located events, at which we expected a larger gathering of people, took place in outdoor locations.

2.7 The schedule of the competition

The complete schedule of the competition and associated events is presented below (Figure 1.6).

	AM (09.30 - 13.00)	PM (14.00 - 17.30)	Evening (18.30 onwards)
Monday 6th Sep*	Venue set up	Venue set up	
Tuesday 7th Sep*	Team set up	Team set up/ general rehearsal	Inaugural event
Wednesday 8th Sep	Competition	Competition	
Thursday 9th Sep	Competition	Competition	
Friday 10th Sep	Competition	Competition	Awards Ceremony Robots, Smart Cities and Inclusion - researchers meet citizens**

* Access restricted to teams and staff
 ** 19:30 - Cortile Guido Fanti - Piazza Maggiore, 6, 40121 Bologna B0

Figure 1.6 SciRoc 2021 Event Schedule

The event venue was available to the competition for five days: from Monday 6th of September 2021, to Friday 10th of September 2021.

Monday and Tuesday were designated to the initial set up of the competition and episode infrastructure, including fitting of the internal space, setting up power and ethernet connections for the teams and each episode, preparing the main team area, assembling the episode sets, etc. OCSA worked with the venue to provide many aspects of the infrastructure and technical equipment and assist the SciRoc team with the set-up. OCSA also sponsored the event and provided a full streaming service at a discounted cost. This was essential to allow remote teams to participate in the competition, and also to allow audience members who could not travel to Italy due to the Coronavirus restrictions, to watch the full event.

By Tuesday the majority of the set-up was complete and so teams were permitted to enter the competition venue to familiarise themselves with the arena, locate their robots and equipment from the secure storage area and prepare for the competition.

Tuesday evening marked the official start of the competition, with an inaugural event. This event took place at Palazzo Re Enzo, with Prof. Valentina Presutti (our main organizer and host in Bologna) introducing SciRoc and Prof. Antonino Rotolo (Vice-Rector, University of Bologna) officially opening the competition and welcoming teams. This was a great opportunity for teams, staff members and sponsors to meet prior to the competition days. Aperitifs were provided and the event was live streamed, with remote teams joining us via video link to ensure they were involved in the full event.

The competition days (Wednesday, Thursday and Friday) were organised according to a strict schedule (Figure 1.7).

Figure 1.7(a) SciRoc Competition Schedule - Day 1 & 2

Figure 1.7(b) SciRoc Competition Schedule - Day 3

Figure 1.7(a) shows the detailed schedule for Day 1 and 2 of the competition. The schedule took into account each team and the episodes they were competing in, allowing sufficient preparation time between participation slots. The location of the episodes was also considered, allowing sufficient time for teams to move equipment from one room to another.

The competition started each morning at 09.30 with a daily briefing, outlining safety procedures and the schedule for the day. PAL Robotics, a key sponsor of the event, contributed with a live demo on each day of the event, followed by a lunch break and the competition restarting for the afternoon session at 14.00. All afternoon trials aimed to finish by 17.00 allowing teams the evening to work on their robots and prepare for the next day. All teams and staff members were required to leave the venue by 20.00.

Figure 1.7(b) shows the detailed schedule for Day 3 of the competition which was devoted to the episode finales and determining the competition winners. On Day 3 we held the Awards Ceremony, conducted by Valentina Presutti and Daniele Nardi, to present the winning teams with their trophies. Again, our remote teams joined by video link.

On the evening of Day 3 we also held a public debate open to the citizens of Bologna as an opportunity to meet our researchers and share any questions, comments or concerns.

2.8 The sponsors

Event Partners:

- University of Bologna (UNIBO)
- Alma Mater Foundation (FAM)
- Foundation for Urban Innovations (FIU)

Competition sponsors:

- PAL Robotics
- Comune Di Bologna
- Il Sole 24 Ore Nova

- Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies (CNR-ISTC)
- Bonfiglioli
- DIVE-IN
- OCSA

Episode sponsors:

- PAL Robotics
- Ocado Technology
- Milton Keynes Council
- Cranfield University

2.9 Branding and trophies

2.9.1 Branding

The following forms of branding were used throughout the competition:

- Large external banners
- Posters and pull-up banners
- Event brochures
- Media Partnership
- T-shirts
- Lanyards
- Streaming and videos
- Sponsored episodes

A large external banner was displayed at the front of the competition venue the week before and week during the event (Figure 1.8a).

Pull up banners (Figure 1.8b) and posters (Figure 1.8c) were also displayed throughout the venue during the competition to direct guests and provide information on the event and the individual episodes. All materials contained a QR code which guests could scan to be directed to the SciRoc website and event brochure (available in both English and Italian) for more detailed information and descriptions (Figure 1.8d).

T-shirts containing the SciRoc, ERL and sponsor logos were worn by all event volunteers so guests could easily identify who to speak to for information and to answer any questions. Lanyards containing security passes, also branded with the SciRoc logo, were also worn by all volunteers and staff members throughout the competition.

Figure 1.8a Large SciRoc banner on display at Palazzo Re Enzo.

Figure 1.8b SciRoc internal pull-up banner

Figure 1.8c SciRoc internal poster

Figure 1.8d SciRoc internal poster

OCSA, one of our event sponsors, provided a full streaming service throughout the entire event. All aspects of the event were streamed live via YouTube, including the welcome evening and opening speeches, and awards ceremony and closing event. All streamed footage is still available to watch via the dedicated SciRoc event channels. OCSA also used this footage to create a promotional video following the event. This video is showcased on the SciRoc website and was distributed via social media channels.

Sponsored episodes included branding provided by the sponsors (Figure 1.9).

Figure 1.9a PAL Robotics branding

2.9.2 Trophies

The winners of each episode were presented with a certificate and trophy (Figure 1.10) to congratulate them on their success and to commemorate the win. All competition participants were also presented with a certificate of participation to thank them for their attendance and efforts.

2.10 Co-located events

During the SciRoc event, a public debate was also co-located to provide a platform for the citizens of Bologna to meet our researchers.

The debate took place at Cortile Guido Fanti, Piazza Maggiore, opposite the competition venue, in the main square of Bologna. The debate (Figure 1.11) was held in an outdoor setting to reduce the risks of COVID-19, and was an opportunity for citizens to meet our researchers to discuss Robots, Smart Cities and Inclusion. Our panel of four experts consisted of:

1. Valentina Presutti (University of Bologna)
2. Daniele Nardi (University of Rome)
3. Francesco Ferro (PAL Robotics)
4. Olga Capirci (Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies)

Our panel invited members of the public to share their questions, concerns and comments. The debate was aimed at citizens of Bologna and attracted an audience of 30 - 40 people.

Figure 1.11 SciRoc panel at the public debate

3.0 The competition

In this section we describe the five robotic challenges, called *episodes*, that were performed in the SciRoc 2 challenge as follows:

(E01) [Coffee Shop](#)

(E02) [Sign Language Generation / Interpretation](#)

(E03) [Shopping Cart](#)

(E04) [Delivery of Emergency Medicines](#)

(E05) [Shopping Pick & Pack](#)

For each episode below we provide a short description (the complete specification can be found in the [rulebooks](#)), the preparation phase, the execution of the competition, the results and some lessons learned

3.1 Episode 01 - Coffee Shop

3.1.1 Episode description

In this episode the robot assisted the staff of a coffee shop to take care of their customers. The robot was required to recognise and report the status of all tables inside the shop, to take orders from customers and to deliver objects to and from the customers' tables.

The main functionalities that were evaluated in this episode are people perception and object perception. It is worth mentioning that the robot had to provide other functionalities (although not explicitly targeted in the score) including navigation, speech synthesis, and spoken language.

This episode has been proposed in *two modalities*: a simulated mode with the Gazebo simulator or with actual robots. Moreover, the teams have been allowed to participate in the competition both remotely and onsite. Notice that remote participation is possible also on real robots, since a TIAGo robot was available to run the code provided by remote participants. Hence, the set of the possible modalities are: *on-site with real robot*, *remote with real robot*, *remote simulated*.

Moreover, in connection with Episode 2, it was also proposed to have interaction through sign language. It is worth noting that the sign language component has not been made available in the simulated scenario, but was available in the real robot version, even if no team took advantage of it.

The *Simulation* and the Remote with the Real Robot *versions* of this episode have been proposed for teams who were unable to travel to the event due to COVID related restrictions. The goal of the simulation environment is to allow for the development of the whole architecture, main functionalities as Person and Object perception are simplified by the simulation set up. Other functionalities needed are navigation and, optionally, Spoken Language to interact with customers. In the case of Spoken Language the Spoken Language interpretation is up to the team, while the text-to-speech is provided by the TIAGo voice. The simulation environment can be regarded as a starting basis for the development of the real robot system. The simulation environment is in Gazebo, where a model of the TIAGo robot and a model of the coffee shop environment are available. The robot is equipped with a tray for transporting a few small objects, and sensors for people/object perception and navigation in the virtual environment. All the sensors available on the TIAGo are accessible in the simulation environment. Notably, the microphone and the camera of the PC, where the simulation environment is running are also available to support multi modal human robot interaction via the simulator. In this way, the interaction with the user took place through a real user located at the competition venue.

3.1.2 Preparation phase

The rulebook of EP01 was released in May 2021. Then, in June, a first set of objects were released. Later, at the beginning of August, as required by the rulebook, the official set of objects for the simulation and for the real scenario were published. For the simulation the objects have been prepared within the official simulator. For the onsite participation, a set of photos for each of the actual objects was provided.

In Bologna, the technical committee prepared a TIAGo robot for the participants. The TIAGo has an arm and a hand with five fingers, capable of integrating the EP02 capabilities for teams that want to deploy sign recognition in the EP01. A private gitlab repository was created and shared with all the participants. The repository contained a docker image provided by PAL robotics with a complete simulated environment provided by the technical committee. The repository also included the instructions related to downloading, running the docker and detailed documentation about the simulation environment and the TIAGo robot.

In the simulated environment, a virtual coffee shop (e.g. 5 metres * 9 metres), with a few tables and typical objects (e.g. coffee cups, napkins, etc.) was made available to resemble the real competition arena in Bologna. The environment consisted of people waiting to be served,

customers already served, tables that needed to be cleaned, and empty tables ready to receive new customers (see Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1 Simulated scenario of EP01

3.1.3 Teams

Teams participated in the three proposed modalities, with three participating in the simulation and three in the on-site fashion. Among those teams, two were in person and one remotely (see Table 1.1).

TEAM	PARTICIPATION MODALITY:
Gravastars (University of West Attica)	Simulated
JEMARO (Università degli studi di Genova)	On-site
LASR (University of Leeds & King's College London)	Simulated
S.M.A.R.T. (New York University Abu Dhabi)	Simulated
SocRob@Home (Instituto Superior Técnico)	On-site remotely
The Repliers (Reply)	On-site

Table. 1.1 Teams and participation modalities of EP01

3.1.4 Running the Competition

After a setup phase, the competition started on September 8th and lasted 3 days, during which a total number of 5 runs were scheduled for the simulated modality and 6 for the on-site partition. A detailed report of the runs and the results is reported in section 3.1.5.

Both in the simulated and in the onsite competition, there has been an improvement of the performances and, in both modalities, some teams were able to complete a run with all the achievements.

In order to guarantee the realistic representation of the real coffee shop scenario, a set of volunteers from the University of Bologna helped to interact with the robot and acted as customers (see Figure 2.2).

No team chose to have the signed interaction with the robot hence, all the runs, in both the modalities, adopted the interaction by voice and with text in some run of the simulated modality.

Figure 2.2 A run of the onsite EP01 with the TIAGo robot interacting with a customer

3.1.5 Results

The following table shows the results of the on-site competition in Bologna with a team participating remotely (SocRob@Home) and two teams participating in person.

SCIROC2 EPISODE1 COFFEE SHOP												
SCORE SHEET												
ON-SITE												
	8 September				9 September				10 September			
	RUN1		RUN2		RUN3		RUN4		FINAL - RUN 1		FINAL - RUN 2	
	Achievements	Penalties	Achievements	Penalties	Achievements	Penalties	Achievements	Penalties	Achievements	Penalties	Achievements	Penalties
SocRob@Home	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	3	0
The Repliers	1	0	6	0	4	0	2	0	6	0	8	0
JEMARO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0

Table. 1.2 Score Sheet of the onsite modality of EP01

The final rank of the on-site participation is the following:

Final Rank:	
1	The Repliers (see Figure 2.3)
2	SocRob@Home
3	JEMARO

Table. 1.3 Final rank of the onsite modality of EP01

A photo of the winner team of the onsite is shown below:

Figure 2.3 Winner of the onsite modality of EP01

And also the JEMARO team (see Figure 2.4) has been awarded in the ceremony for the Most Sociable Robot:

Figure 2.4 Awarding ceremony of the Most Sociable Robot

For the simulated version of the challenge, three teams participated remotely, one that was already involved in the on-site withdrew. The following table shows the results:

SCIROC2 EPISODE1 COFFEE SHOP										
SCORE SHEET										
SIMULATION										
	8 September				9 September				10 September	
	RUN1		RUN2		RUN3		RUN4		FINAL	
	Achievements	Penalties								
S.M.A. R.T.	5	0	5	0	5	0	8	0	10	0
Gravastars	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	6	0
JEMAR O	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LASR	1	0	5	0	0	0	5	0	6	0

Table. 1.4 Score Sheet of the simulated modality of EP01

At the end of the simulated participation, we had an exequo in the second place according to this final rank:

Final Rank:		
1	S.M.A.R.T.	
2	Gravastars	LASR

Table. 1.5 Final rank of the simulated modality of EP01

Figure 2.5 shows the awarding ceremony of the simulated modality of EP01.

Figure 2.5 Awarding ceremony of the simulated modality of EP01

3.1.6 Lessons Learned

In this episode three participation modalities have been proposed to teams. This allowed us to explore the different benchmark setups to better evaluate the performance of an autonomous agent. In all the proposed setups, we had great results, with all the teams capable of competing in the challenge with a unique code base provided through the use of a Docker container. By taking a look at the perspective of simulated and real robot competition, we had teams gaining all the achievements of the runs. We collected feedback from the participants and we obtained representations of the weaknesses in the simulated and the onsite modalities. One of the main limitations, especially for remote onsite participation, has been the duration of the setup phase. In fact, the setup time should have been longer in order to make the remote teams capable of bridging the gap with respect to the onsite teams. On the other hand, simulations suffered from a non standardised set of devices to interact with the simulated environment. In fact, especially the microphone used for the remote interaction was an element of uncertainty for some of the involved teams and a solution could have been to choose and communicate the microphone model before the competition.

Audio noise has been an issue also for onsite participation during the most crowded runs but this can be seen as a challenge in a Cocktail Party problem once the hardware is known. For the future competitions, object manipulation can be added and the interaction with the customers can be increased.

In the goal of reaching a standardisation of the testbed for robotic applications, this episode represented a promising starting point providing several testing modalities that dispense the users to create ad hoc testing environments and allowing to compare software in a controlled scenario.

3.2 Episode 02 - Sign Language Generation / Interpretation

3.2.1 Episode description

In the context of the Coffee Shop assistant robot proposed by EP01, an essential step towards the concept of inclusiveness, is undoubtedly the possibility for the robot to understand and perform sign language (SL). In this episode, we divided SL into two macro-categories: sign language execution (generation) and sign language recognition (interpretation) (see Figure 2.6). In the recognition phase, the robot must be able to recognize 2 simple signs and 1 composed sign effectively and be able to correctly trace the evolution of hand movements to extract the meaning of 1 sentence composed of several different signs performed by LIS experts. In the execution phase, the robot must be able to execute 1 simple sign, 1 composed sign and 1 sentence accordingly. The signs taken into consideration are signs specifically designed to facilitate the interaction between consumers and waiters in the context of the Coffee Shop.

Figure 2.6 (a) Sign language recognition (interpretation) and (b) sign language execution (generation)

The tasks performed by the robots were:

- Recognizing the first two simple signs
- Recognizing the second sign

- Recognizing the sentence
- Executing the simple sign
- Executing the composed sign
- Executing the sentence sign

The performance of the sign language execution by the robot has been evaluated also on the basis of user's perception through specific questionnaires filled by Italian Sign Language (LIS) experts.

Figure 2.7 Pictures taken at the competition illustrating the LIS experts of EP02

EP02 is executed in two independent sections of sign language recognition and sign language execution and an award is given for each section. The sign language recognition has been evaluated by the achievements of the robot's recognition performance, while the sign language execution has been evaluated by the achievements of the results of the questionnaires filled out by the LIS experts. Three experts (see Figure 2.7) participated in the sign language execution evaluation study in each run. The technical committee collected all the answers and verified if the team got an achievement on users' perceptions in each performance.

3.2.2 Preparation phase

The rulebook of EP02 was released in May 2021. For this episode, an area of 20 m² has been used for the competition (see in Figure 2.8).

Figure 2.8 Competition area of EP02

The technical committee prepared a TIAGo robot for the participants of EP02. The TIAGo has an arm and a hand with five fingers to support both the sign recognition scenario and sign execution scenario. A private gitlab repository was created and shared with all the participants. The repository contained a docker image provided by PAL robotics. The repository also included the instructions related to downloading, running the docker and detailed documentation about the simulation environment and the TIAGo robot. A game controller was prepared in order to manage EP02. One of the main contributions of EP02 in the phase of preparation is the dataset.

The dataset was collected through the contribution of several experts of Italian Sign Language of the SILIS (Gruppo per lo Studio e l'Informazione sulla Lingua dei Segni Italiana) group of Rome. It represents various terms related to the world of bars and restaurants. With the help of the experts, signs and sign variants were selected that were compatible with the hardware of the PAL robotics TIAGo robot. The collection of data has been a critical element in realising this episode, being indeed one of the essential elements of this type of application. In fact, the complexity of sign language requires the contribution of highly specialised experts to create a consistent and correct dataset for its intended use.

3.2.3 Teams

The participating teams were:

UNIBAS team, with researchers coming from the University of Basilicata. The team participated in both sections, sign language recognition and sign language execution. The team participated in the challenge employing the TIAGo robot.

SPQR Coconuts team, with master students from the University of Rome, La Sapienza. The team participated in both sections, sign language recognition and sign language execution. The team participated in the challenge employing the TIAGo robot.

The repliers team initially registered for EP02, but did not participate.

3.2.4 Running the Competition

SCIROC2 EPISODE2 SIGN LANGUAGE						
SCORE SHEET						
ACHIEVEMENTS						
		8 September		9 September		10 September
		RUN1	-	RUN2	RUN3	FINAL
The Repliers	Generation	-		-	-	-
	Interpretation	-		-	-	-
UniBas	Generation	0		0	-	0
	Interpretation	-		-	0	1
SPQR CocoNuts	Generation	4		6	-	10
	Interpretation	-		-	0	-

Table 1.6. Score sheet of EP02

The competition lasted 3 days, during which a total number of 4 runs of EP02 were scheduled; 3 general runs were performed in the first 2 days, while the final run was performed on the last day.

The technical committee noted an improvement in performance during the competition days. Both two teams qualified for the final run.

LIS experts were involved to fill out the questionnaires for the evaluation study. In any run, the same LIS experts were involved to evaluate all the teams performance regarding the sign language execution in that run.

3.2.5 Results

Global results of EP02 are reported in the table above (Table 1.6). For each run, achievements for each team are reported. The winner of the sign language generation section of EP02 was the SPQR Coconuts team from the University of Rome, La Sapienza. The winner of the sign language interpretation section of E02 was the UNIBAS team (Figure 2.9).

Figure 2.9: Winners of EP02, (a) SPQR Coconuts team, winner of Sign language generation; (b) Unibas team, winner of Sign language interpretation

As an exploitation of the competition results, we are performing a more detailed analysis of the results of the questionnaires, aimed at a scientific publication, possibly also involving the participating teams.

3.2.6 Lessons Learned

The concept of inclusiveness is fundamental to modern society. For this reason, robotics and artificial intelligence must take essential steps to make the services offered by the most modern technologies usable by the largest possible number of people. This goal implies the need for robots to also provide their services to people with special needs. “Sign language generation / interpretation”, in particular, “Italian sign language generation / interpretation” in the field of Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) is a novel topic that addresses inclusiveness. To explore the interaction through sign languages developed by and for deaf people, we focused on a set of signs in the context of a coffee shop in EP02. The participating teams of EP02 saw remarkable improvement during the competition with the help of LIS experts. Our LIS experts explained slight differences between the signs and recommended the participating teams to address the shape of signs, the movements of palm and the directions of signs.

During SciRoc EP02, a fundamental aspect was the deaf community's involvement both in the organisation of the episode and its development. In the evaluation of the robot's performance, it was essential to have a team of experts both for the production and for the review of the signs themselves. In fact, the complexity of the language, both in its structure and in its execution, makes it extremely difficult to produce and replicate the data without the help of a language expert. In addition, the collaboration already in the early stages of the project led to

greater involvement of the deaf community and the participants themselves, also helping to create an emotional bonding towards the robot.

3.3 Episode 03 - Shopping Cart

3.3.1 Episode description

EP03 is the result of a collaboration between European projects SciRoc and Eurobench (<https://eurobench2020.eu/>). EP03 is in fact a version of Eurobench's BEAST (*Benchmark-Enabling Active Shopping Trolley*) benchmark for mobile robots.

The following picture shows the benchmark as installed at Palazzo Re Enzo in Bologna for the SciRoc Challenge.

Figure 2.10: Testbed of EP03 as installed in Palazzo Re Enzo, Bologna

The testbed of EP03 comprises two main elements:

- the arena, i.e. the passive structured environment where the benchmark takes place;
- the active shopping cart, i.e. a robotized shopping cart capable of behaviours which include, but are not limited to, that of a standard cart.

The aim of this benchmark is to evaluate the capability of a mobile robot to correctly manoeuvre a wheeled device (shopping cart or walker). In this context, “correctly manoeuvring” involves performance metrics concerning geometry (such as staying close to a

predefined trajectory or maximising distance from obstacles), time, force (e.g., smooth application of force to the handle over time instead of abrupt bursts). The BEAST benchmark makes use of the capability of the active shopping cart to simulate physical disturbances that occur in real-world scenarios, such as unevenly distributed wheel friction or small obstacles on the ground (such as a low step or a pebble). For what concerns the version of EP03 executed in Bologna in 2021, the measurement devices incorporated into the shopping cart and the capability of the cart to introduce disturbances into its motion have not been employed.

The BEAST arena is a passive structural element that the robot under test is expected to enter. The benchmark requires that the robot operates the shopping cart within the arena, which is a rectangular area of 3m by 6m. The walls of the arena are composed of 1m tall panels. The following image is a rendering of the arena.

Figure 2.11: CAD representation of the testbed of EP03, showing the expected trajectory of the shopping cart

The image also shows the trajectory that the cart (pushed by the robot) is expected to follow during the execution of the benchmark, going from its initial position (purple) to its final one (green). Orange pillars are used to determine the trajectory to the robot: for instance, the first part is perfectly rectilinear, while the subsequent part is expected to curve around a central pillar.

The BEAST active shopping cart is a robotized version of a commercial cart. The following image shows the resulting device.

Figure 2.12: Active shopping trolley of EP03

In order to become part of the benchmark, the cart has been modified by removing the two front wheels, and replacing them with the drive unit which enables fine control of the braking torque on each wheel. In this configuration, the front wheels are fixed while the rear wheels are pivoting. The cart handle has been instrumented with two load cells to measure the horizontal force applied by the user to push the cart. Finally, a laser scanner has been installed above the drive unit. The output of this sensor is used by BEAST to localise the cart in the testbed and to measure the distance between the cart and the obstacles.

3.3.2 Preparation phase

The testbed of EP03 is a self-contained unit not depending on external infrastructure except for lighting and composed of modular elements. As a consequence, its installation at the venue has been straightforward. The following image shows the entrance of the room as it presented itself to the public.

Figure 2.13: The setup of EP03 as it presented itself to the public of the SciRoc Challenge

3.3.3 Teams

Three teams were expected to execute EP03, i.e.

- team BlueWave from Tarbiat Modares University of Tehran, Iran
- team ALMATRON from University of Bologna, Italy
- team Hybots from The Open University + Politecnico di Milano, respectively UK and Italy

Unfortunately, due to cancellations caused by the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, in the end only the last team were able to participate. For this they used their own TIAGo robot, brought from the UK.

With there being only one team, time pressures were reduced and competition was not the issue, so the episode organisers and the participating team both had the possibility of exploiting the SciRoc Challenge to thoroughly validate and refine their implementations, which is usually not possible in more frantic competition settings.

The following photos show the execution of EP03 during the 2nd SciRoc Challenge by team Hybots.

Figure 2.14: The PAL Tiago robot of team Hybots (Open University + Politecnico di Milano) executing EP03

3.3.4 Running the Competition

Unfortunately, the participating team incurred delays in the shipping of their robot from the UK to Italy, and was not able to prepare before the competition. The robot arrived in Italy only a short time before the challenge.

In the end, due to this and to the fact that there was only one participating team, the rules were relaxed and the team was allowed to add sensory aids to the cart (QR codes used to identify the position of the cart relative to the robot). This allowed the Hybots team to execute a simplified version of EP03, doable with the short on site preparation phase.

3.3.5 Results

Although the Hybots team kept working on their system throughout the entire duration of the competition, their robot did not reach the stage where it was able to complete the episode. For this reason a score could not be assigned to their runs.

3.3.6 Lessons Learned

Due to the single competitor which actually showed up (the Hybots team) and the very relaxed agenda this enabled, the whole experience of EP03 in Bologna has been more akin to an extended rehearsal than to a competition. As such, it has been useful not only for Hybots, but also for SciRoc: in fact the unusual conditions (and especially the absence of the time pressures typically associated with competitions) allowed the organisers more time to validate and fine-tune the episode in a real-world context.

The main lesson learned by the execution of EP03 is that it is indeed a viable benchmark for autonomous robots. Its setup proved to be easily transported and installed (as intended through modular design) and the task suitable for the capabilities of today's mobile manipulators and humanoid robots.

3.4 Episode 04 - Delivery of Emergency Medicines

3.4.1 Episode description

A medicine is ordered by a person in Bologna that cannot go out (due to quarantine-related issues or because the person is disabled). The robot must be able to move autonomously to the location where the citizen is waiting. The robot might need to detect and avoid possible obstacles on the way (static and dynamic), and it must consider that GPS coverage is not always guaranteed. Once the robot arrives at the citizen's location, the robot should interact with him/her (in English) to deliver the proper medicine. Depending on the person's health, it could also be possible that the robot will need to accompany the person to the nearest medical centre to see a doctor.

3.4.2 Preparation phase

A labyrinthine scenario was prepared with movable modules, allowing it to easily change its shape and prepare different configurations with increasing difficulty.

Figure 2.15 Scenario of EP04

3.4.3 Teams

Two teams initially expressed interest in the episode, but only one team finally participated in the challenge:

- Pathfinders, 3 mechatronic master's students from FH Aachen, Germany.

Figure 2.16 Team Pathfinders robot of EP04

3.4.4 Running the Competition

With only one team, there was no need to arrange a schedule, since they had free access to the episode arena over the competition days.

At the beginning, they faced hardware-power issues on their platform. The last day they could finally run complete tests.

3.4.5 Results

SCIROC E04 SCORE	
TEAM	Achievements
Pathfinders	8/12

Table 1.7 Score sheet of EP04

Figure 2.17: Winners of EP04, Team Pathfinders

3.4.6 Lessons Learned

- Given the size of the single participating robot, the scenario was ok, but if larger robots were to participate, a bigger, more complex and challenging scenario would have been required.
- Teams could be contacted for details of their robot platforms and check if they are suitable for the challenge arrangements.
- To increase team participation, teams could be contacted for feedback on what could have made them apply for this challenge, and what kept them back from doing so.
- Providing a robot platform, like a PAL TIAGo, may encourage more teams to participate, like with other episodes.

3.5 Episode 05 - Shopping Pick & Pack

3.5.1 Episode description

This episode addresses the problem of picking products from a storage container and placing them on a designated shelf. The chosen domain is the operation of an autonomous shop, where the robot helps to manage the inventory of a shop and to organise newly arrived products. The main functionality tested in this episode is *mobile manipulation* using an autonomous robot. In recent years, mobile manipulation has become a problem of interest among researchers due to the variety and complexity of challenges and robot capabilities that are involved. This episode “Shopping: Pick and Pack (EP05)” contributes in benchmarking mobile manipulation abilities of robots also focusing on a realistic business scenario. In this episode, the challenge includes picking grocery items from a storage container and organising items on designated shelves.

Figure 2.18 Competition arena of EP05

3.5.2 Preparation phase

In-order to mitigate against the uncertainty regarding team travel, the competition was divided into 2 separate categories:

1. On-site main competition
2. Remote competition

The separate events were created such that even if teams were not able to participate in the on-site event, they could participate in the remote competition, which amounts to performing at their own site and being monitored and evaluated from the competition site using cameras and zoom connection.

The teams which responded to the call for participation were briefed about the format of the competition and the rulebook was explained to the participants. All further information about the competition was continuously updated via the shared rulebook.

Since the teams were required to test their solutions before the competitions, all the manipulation items/objects which were required by the teams were provided by our sponsor Ocado and shipped to the participants 2 weeks in advance.

For the remote competition, the expected arena setup and different object locations in the box was given to the teams on the first day of the competition. Zoom was used as the medium for monitoring of the event.

For the onsite competition, shelves and containers were bought from the local market in Bologna and the objects were provided by Ocado. The location of the shelves in the arena was fixed based on the location provided by the local organiser, the robot capabilities and better visibility of audiences.

3.5.3 Teams

In total 5 teams participated in the event. For the onsite event 2 teams participated and for the remote event 3 teams participated. The participating team names are shared in the table below.

Team Name	Organization	Event
AutonOhm	Nuremberg Tech	onsite
HyBots	The Open University & Politecnico di Milano	onsite
b-it-bots	Hochschule Bonn-Rhein-Sieg	online
LASR	University of Leeds & King's College London	online
Team Cranfield	Cranfield University	online

Table 1.8 Participating teams of EP05

3.5.4 Running the Competition

In order to accommodate both the online and the on-site event the times were divided into 15 minutes slots and were equally divided among all the teams. Below is the schedule for the event.

	09:30	09:45	10:00	10:15	10:30	10:45	11:00	11:15	11:30	11:45	12:00	12:15
Wed			B	L	C	B	L	C				
Thur			B	L	C					B	L	C
Fri			L	B	C		Finals					

Table 1.9 Schedule of EP05

14:00	14:15	14:30	14:45	15:00	15:15	15:30	15:45	16:00	16:15	16:30	16:45	17:00	17:15	17:30	17:45
A		H		A		A		H		A		Extra		Extra	
A		H		A		A		A		L	B	C	L	Extra	
B	L	C	B	A	B	C	L		C	A	L				

	Episode
A	AutonOHM
B	b-it-bots
C	Team Cranfield
H	Hybots
L	LASR

For the remote competition the teams were provided with the zoom link. The zoom link was kept open for all 3 days from morning 9:00 till evening 18:00 . The teams were instructed to join 5 minutes before the run and share their screen. The teams were asked to have 2 cameras, one focusing on the basket and the other focusing on the robot.

The onsite event was run in parallel to the online event. Two teams participated in the onsite event. For better communication with the local audience of Bologna there was an italian translator who would answer all the queries from the audience. The teams during the runs were also asked to explain what the robot was doing so that the audience could understand the working of the robotics.

Table 1.10 Different layouts of EP05

3.5.5 Results

Team	Layout	Disqualification	Penalties	Achievements	Time
AutonOHM	1	-	-	-	-
AutonOHM	2	-	-	-	-
AutonOHM	3	-	-	-	-
b-it-bots*	1	no	0	8	6:23
b-it-bots*	2	no	2	12	5:41
b-it-bots*	3	no	0	7	9:01
LASR	1	no	1	20	10:00
LASR	2	no	0	13	10:00
LASR	3	no	0	16	10:00
Team Cranfield	1	no	0	24	4:08
Team Cranfield	2	no	0	23	4:42
Team Cranfield	3	no	0	21	4:44

Table 1.11 Score sheet of EP05

Winners

Event	Winner	
Onsite	AutonOHM	
Online	Team Cranfield	

3.5.6 Lessons Learned

- The main take away from the event was that an online based event is possible for robotics competitions. As most of the teams could not participate, because of the pandemic restrictions, the possibility of remote participation was helpful for them. By sending all the objects to them in advance, the teams were able to show their capabilities from their own lab and the organisers were able to benchmark the robot capability.

- Industry sponsored events with a valid industry problem help to get more teams interested in the event. We should focus on getting more industry and real world unsolved problems to attract more roboticists around the world.
- Creating a REST API based logging and scoring mechanism helped in automating the scoring of the online events and benchmarking the progress made by teams over the week.
- The competition provided a good prototype for benchmarking robot performance in different labs spread across the world. This is of great importance as this will promote participation of different teams who were not able to participate because of high transportation costs.

4.0 Impacts of the 2nd ERL Smart Cities RObotics Challenge

In this section we report on the impacts of the competition.

4.1 Volunteers and visitors

4.1.1 Volunteers

Volunteers (Figure 3.1) for the 2021 SciRoc event were recruited through the University of Bologna. A volunteer recruitment day was held at the University on Friday 21st May 2021 to encourage students with a related subject area to volunteer at the event. Valentina Presutti and Daniele Nardi were available on the recruitment day to explain the needs of the SciRoc event. Interested candidates could then sign up to volunteer over the course of the event.

Figure 3.1 Volunteers at the 2021 SciRoc Challenge

4.1.2 Visitors

Visitors were invited to attend the event in person free of charge. The event took place in Palazzo Re Enzo, a historic building located in the centre of Bologna. The building is not usually open to the public, and the public can only enter to attend an event. This, along with the fantastic location of the venue, attracted a number of visitors. Over 700 people attended the event over the 3 days of the competition.

At our 2019 event in Milton Keynes the competition took place in a large shopping centre which had a large amount of foot traffic, with passers by stopping to watch the competition. In comparison, attendees for the 2021 event had to visit the venue specifically for the competition. Although the venue is in the main square of Bologna, visitors must pass through a gated entrance and therefore there is no foot traffic or passers by. This did mean that our visitors at the 2021 event were more engaged, asking questions and interacting with our volunteers, researchers and team members as they had come to the venue with the purpose of attending the competition. Our 2019 event however did attract a much larger audience due to the fact that the competition was more accessible for passers by.

Given the restrictions and limitations around the COVID-19 pandemic, and that attendees had to visit the venue specifically for the event, we are very pleased with the number of visitors received for 2021.

As a result of the pandemic the full event was also streamed live via YouTube which attracted an online audience of approx. 1.2k.

Figure 3.2 Visitors watching the 2021 SciRoc competition

4.2 Media coverage

4.2.1 Mainstream Media

For our 2021 event we partnered with the prestigious Il Sole 24 Ore, an Italian national newspaper. Prior to the event our media partner published banner and block advertisements via their online website to disseminate news of the SciRoc competition (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: SciRoc banner advertisement via the Il Sole 24 Ore website

Throughout the event SciRoc was also featured on a number of national and regional news and radio broadcasts, as outlined below:

- 6 September 2021: Valentina Presutti was interviewed on behalf of SciRoc for a Radio 24 podcast. Radio 24 is a national all news radio station in Italy. An article was also published via the Radio 24 website.
- 8 September: SciRoc featured on Rainews, an Italian national news channel.
- 9 September: SciRoc featured on Corriere di Bologna, an Italian regional news platform.
- 9 September: SciRoc featured on BBC News Look East, a UK regional news channel. The BBC news team visited Cranfield University to interview Team Cranfield who were competing remotely in the SciRoc competition.
- 9 September: Valentina Presutti was interviewed at the SciRoc event, this interview then featured on Policinema TV (the dedicated student channel for the Policinema training school of cinema and television).

4.2.2 Social Media and Online

In addition to the media outlined above, news of SciRoc was also disseminated across the SciRoc and European Robotics League websites and social media channels. Dissemination efforts included articles, images, links to useful information, promotional videos and links to the live streaming of the event.

Our efforts saw a 54% increase in Twitter impressions during the month of the competition, compared to the previous 3 months, along with a 77% increase in new followers. This trend continued across our Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn platforms with a clear peak in the audience reach percentage during the month of September.

Following the 2021 event a promotional video showing the full highlights from the competition was also shared across all platforms and all streamed content is still available via the SciRoc YouTube channels. This content has been viewed over 1.2k times.

5.0 Reflections on the 2nd ERL Smart Cities Robotics Challenge

The second SciRoc challenge has been a key milestone towards the establishment of a self supported robotic competition at the EU level. In fact, for the first time the competition was organised by a host city, which provided all the resources (human and financial) to run the event, with the only exception of the technical and scientific support of the SciRoc Consortium in setting up and running the five episodes described in the previous section. This is an unprecedented achievement, which led to a very successful event, despite the difficulties brought about by the COVID-19 pandemics. Below we outline the most significant results.

As reported in Section 2 the impact of the competition towards the general public was extraordinary, given the wonderful location of the competition, at the heart of one of the most beautiful Italian cities. Moreover, the second SciRoc challenge turned out to be the first in person event organised in Bologna and also the first robotic competition since the beginning of the pandemic. Consequently, it was perceived by participants and visitors as a most successful step towards the restart after the pandemic. Moreover, the need to also share the event with teams and interested people, who could not physically attend, led to success on the remote channels that have been set up to stream the whole event.

The implementation of the competition had to face significant challenges due to the uncertainty caused by the pandemic. These challenges were addressed with innovative technical solutions in terms of the arrangements of the competition, as well as with a great effort by all the organisers, local supporters and sponsors.

As for the technical challenges, described in Section 3, the SciRoc project developed and implemented several new concepts: introduction of simulation environment for a service robots scenario (Episode 1); remote participation on a physical robot made available on site thanks to a successful collaboration with PAL Robotics (Episode 1 and 2); introduction of a novel challenge related to sign language that had outstanding success within the deaf community, which was involved from the design of the challenge to its implementation and, currently on the take up of the experience (Episode 2); synergy with the H2020 Eurobench project aiming at implementing benchmarks for robots (Episode 3); design of a new challenge for emergency robots (Episode 4); distributed execution of the competition with both on site and remote participants performing the tests at their own labs (Episode 5).

As for the organisational effort, the SciRoc project has been quite fortunate in partnering with Prof. Valentina Presutti, with the city of Bologna and their team. The local organisers faced the manifold uncertainties caused by the COVID-19 scenario, managing to keep the planning of the activities on track, attracting sponsors and involving the city and the citizens. Much more could have been done in a normal scenario, but what has been achieved, given the circumstances, is truly remarkable.

All the above considerations, make us believe that the second SciRoc challenge has exceeded any expectation in achieving a successful step forward from both a scientific and dissemination point of view, under and beyond the COVID-19 pandemic.

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